

RESECTION SURFACE AREA IN ANATOMIC AND ATYPICAL LIVER RESECTIONS AS A CAUSE OF SPECIFIC POST-RESECTION COMPLICATIONS

Rusenov D.

*Dr., MD, Clinic of liver, biliary pancreatic and general surgery
Acibadem City Clinic Tokuda Hospital EAD Sofia*

Abstract

Despite technical advances and high experience of liver resection of specialized centers, it is still burdened by relatively high rates of postoperative morbidity and mortality. No consensus on the indications for surgical resection. There are a number of factors that are important for determining the type of liver resection.

Keywords: liver resections, complications after liver resections, resection surface.

INTRODUCTION:

It is assumed that with the larger area of the resection surface of the liver, there is a higher risk of occurrence of postresection hemorrhage and bilirrhagia. The more blood vessels and biliary ducts are interrupted and even if they are adequately treated hemostatically and biliostatically at the site of hepatoctomy, the greater the danger that this treatment in one or several places is not sufficiently reliable and leads to complications in the early postoperative period.

OBJECTIVE:

After getting acquainted with as much information as possible on the matter and based on our previous research, we formulated the following goal:

Data collection regarding the size of the resection surface in liver surgery and the occurrence of specific post-resection complications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

For the period from January, 2007 - March, 2018 in Clinic of liver, biliary pancreatic and general surgery, Acibadem City Clinic Tokuda Hospital ,1021 interventions were performed on the liver:

Cases of intervention other than liver resection by definition were excluded ISGLS, "removal of part of the liver parenchyma due to involvement by a disease process or traumatic injury resulting in devitalization of the parenchyma".

Thus, the study did not find the cases of:

- hepatotomy;
- cystotomies and cyst resections, practically without removal of functioning or pathologically altered liver parenchyma;
- liver biopsies, alcoholization of tumors. liver biopsies, alcoholization of tumors;
- interruption of trunk branches of the hepatic artery and/or portal vein with the aim of hypoperfusion of a given area (segments, lobe);
- suture of the liver in trauma;

Thus, a total of 852 cases of liver resections were included in the series

RESULTS:

To confirm or reject the hypothesis that it is not the volume of liver resection (Anatomic resection or Atypical resection) but only the hepatotomy area that is at risk for bleeding or bile leakage, we reviewed the operative protocols in all cases. In this analysis, we included only atypical liver resections, since in all anatomical resections the area of the resection surface was $> 50 \text{ cm}^2$ (Table 1.). We found that with a resection area $> 50 \text{ cm}^2$ we registered a frequency of specific post-resection complications of 13.1%, while with an area $< 50 \text{ cm}^2$ – 10.7%, but without a statistically significant difference between them ($p=0.599$).

Table 1.
Frequency of specific post-resection complications after atypical liver resection depending on the area of the resection surface

Resection surface area	Complication	Statistics	Atypical liver resection n=392	P
$< 50 \text{ cm}^2$	No	N	133	0.599
		%	89.3%	
	Yes	N	16	
		%	10.7%	
$>50 \text{ cm}^2$	No	N	213	
		%	86.9%	
	Yes	N	32	
		%	13.1%	

The reason for the unestablished relationship between the frequency of specific post-resection complications and the area of the resection surface can be found in the fact that with meticulous definitive hemo- and biliostasis (mainly suture ligatures), the risk of occurrence of post-resection hemorrhage and post-resection biliargia is sufficiently reliably prevented.

A resection surface with an area $\geq 57.5 \text{ cm}^2$ remains one of the 10 risk factors for the occurrence of post-resection bilirubin and hemorrhage. [1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16]

DISCUSSION:

In Atypical liver resections and resection area $> 50 \text{ cm}^2$, we recorded a higher frequency of post-resection

hemorrhage and post-resection bilirubin (13.1%), while in area < 50 cm² they affected a smaller percentage of the operated (10.7%), but this fact proved without statistical reliability (p=0.599). To prevent post-resection complications, the surgical technique itself must achieve thorough hemo- and biliostasis of the resection surface

CONCLUSION:

Liver resection surgery should be performed in centers with sufficient experience in this field, working according to established standards and algorithms, and also with well-developed interventional gastroenterology.

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